

Roblox Screener Survey

Start of Block: Default Question Block

Q1 Roblox Game Developer Screener Survey

We are looking for individuals with all levels of experience – even those who have just tried to make a Roblox game. This study aims to help Roblox game developers by identifying the challenges they encounter.

Interviews will be 30-60 minutes long and done over your preferred voice communication channel (e.g. Zoom). Those who are selected for and complete the interview will receive a \$20 Amazon gift card. Participants aged 13-17 require permission from a guardian to join the study, and the guardian must also be present during the interview (they will be separately compensated with a \$20 gift card).

This study is conducted by researchers who are members of [Institution name]. This research has received ethical approval from [Institution name]'s Institutional Review Board (IRB).

Goal: To learn about your experience as a Roblox game developer

Participants needed: Any person that is based in the US, fluent in English, has developed a Roblox game, is aged 13 and up (13-17 require written permission from guardians to join the study and the guardian must be present during the interview)

Expected activities: We will have a 30-60 minute conversation about your experiences as a game developer over your preferred voice communication channel (e.g. Zoom). These will be recorded for transcription and data analysis purposes.

Compensation: If you are selected for the interview, you will receive a \$20 Amazon gift card upon completion of the interview

Data protection: We respect your privacy and won't be sharing any collected information with people outside of the research team. **No identifiable information will be kept or published, and all data will be destroyed upon completion of the study.**

Feel free to email me at [Email address of the researcher] with any questions or concerns.

Q2 If you are interested in participating in our interview study, you may proceed with this survey. You may skip any questions you don't feel comfortable answering.

I understand (1)

Q3 Are you a Roblox game developer or a parent/guardian of a Roblox game developer?

- Roblox game developer (1)
- Parent/guardian of a Roblox game developer (2)

Q5 In which country do you currently reside?

- Afghanistan (1)
- Albania (2)
- Algeria (3)
- Andorra (4)
- Angola (5)
- Antigua and Barbuda (6)
- Argentina (7)
- Armenia (8)
- Australia (9)
- Austria (10)
- Azerbaijan (11)
- Bahamas (12)
- Bahrain (13)
- Bangladesh (14)
- Barbados (15)
- Belarus (16)
- Belgium (17)
- Belize (18)
- Benin (19)
- Bhutan (20)

- Bolivia (21)
- Bosnia and Herzegovina (22)
- Botswana (23)
- Brazil (24)
- Brunei Darussalam (25)
- Bulgaria (26)
- Burkina Faso (27)
- Burundi (28)
- Cambodia (29)
- Cameroon (30)
- Canada (31)
- Cape Verde (32)
- Central African Republic (33)
- Chad (34)
- Chile (35)
- China (36)
- Colombia (37)
- Comoros (38)
- Congo, Republic of the... (39)
- Costa Rica (40)
- Côte d'Ivoire (41)

- Croatia (42)
- Cuba (43)
- Cyprus (44)
- Czech Republic (45)
- Democratic Republic of the Congo (47)
- Denmark (48)
- Djibouti (49)
- Dominica (50)
- Dominican Republic (51)
- Ecuador (52)
- Egypt (53)
- El Salvador (54)
- Equatorial Guinea (55)
- Eritrea (56)
- Estonia (57)
- Ethiopia (58)
- Fiji (59)
- Finland (60)
- France (61)
- Gabon (62)
- Gambia (63)

- Georgia (64)
- Germany (65)
- Ghana (66)
- Greece (67)
- Grenada (68)
- Guatemala (69)
- Guinea (70)
- Guinea-Bissau (71)
- Guyana (72)
- Haiti (73)
- Honduras (74)
- Hong Kong (S.A.R.) (75)
- Hungary (76)
- Iceland (77)
- India (78)
- Indonesia (79)
- Iran (80)
- Iraq (81)
- Ireland (82)
- Israel (83)
- Italy (84)

- Jamaica (85)
- Japan (86)
- Jordan (87)
- Kazakhstan (88)
- Kenya (89)
- Kiribati (90)
- Kuwait (91)
- Kyrgyzstan (92)
- Lao People's Democratic Republic (93)
- Latvia (94)
- Lebanon (95)
- Lesotho (96)
- Liberia (97)
- Libyan Arab Jamahiriya (98)
- Liechtenstein (99)
- Lithuania (100)
- Luxembourg (101)
- Madagascar (102)
- Malawi (103)
- Malaysia (104)
- Maldives (105)

- Mali (106)
- Malta (107)
- Marshall Islands (108)
- Mauritania (109)
- Mauritius (110)
- Mexico (111)
- Micronesia, Federated States of... (112)
- Monaco (113)
- Mongolia (114)
- Montenegro (115)
- Morocco (116)
- Mozambique (117)
- Myanmar (118)
- Namibia (119)
- Nauru (120)
- Nepal (121)
- Netherlands (122)
- New Zealand (123)
- Nicaragua (124)
- Niger (125)
- Nigeria (126)

- North Korea (127)
- Norway (128)
- Oman (129)
- Pakistan (130)
- Palau (131)
- Panama (132)
- Papua New Guinea (133)
- Paraguay (134)
- Peru (135)
- Philippines (136)
- Poland (137)
- Portugal (138)
- Qatar (139)
- Republic of Moldova (141)
- Romania (142)
- Russian Federation (143)
- Rwanda (144)
- Saint Kitts and Nevis (145)
- Saint Lucia (146)
- Saint Vincent and the Grenadines (147)
- Samoa (148)

- San Marino (149)
- Sao Tome and Principe (150)
- Saudi Arabia (151)
- Senegal (152)
- Serbia (153)
- Seychelles (154)
- Sierra Leone (155)
- Singapore (156)
- Slovakia (157)
- Slovenia (158)
- Solomon Islands (159)
- Somalia (160)
- South Africa (161)
- South Korea (162)
- Spain (163)
- Sri Lanka (164)
- Sudan (165)
- Suriname (166)
- Swaziland (167)
- Sweden (168)
- Switzerland (169)

- Syrian Arab Republic (170)
- Tajikistan (171)
- Thailand (172)
- The former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia (173)
- Timor-Leste (174)
- Togo (175)
- Tonga (176)
- Trinidad and Tobago (177)
- Tunisia (178)
- Turkey (179)
- Turkmenistan (180)
- Tuvalu (181)
- Uganda (182)
- Ukraine (183)
- United Arab Emirates (184)
- United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland (185)
- United Republic of Tanzania (186)
- United States of America (187)
- Uruguay (188)
- Uzbekistan (189)
- Vanuatu (190)

- Venezuela, Bolivarian Republic of... (191)
- Viet Nam (192)
- Yemen (193)
- Zambia (580)
- Zimbabwe (1357)

End of Block: Default Question Block

Start of Block: RBLX Game Devs

Q4 How old are you? *If you are under 18, we need to get a signed consent form from your parent or guardian and will also be scheduling the interview through them.*

Q6 How do you describe yourself?

- Male (1)
- Female (2)
- Non-binary / third gender (3)
- Prefer to self-describe (4) _____
- Prefer not to say (5)

Q7 Are you of Spanish, Hispanic, or Latino origin?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Q9 Choose one or more races that you consider yourself to be:

White or Caucasian (1)

Black or African American (2)

American Indian/Native American or Alaska Native (3)

Asian (4)

Middle Eastern or North African (5)

Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander (6)

Other (7)

Q10 How long have you played Roblox? *Please specify if years or months.*

Q11 How long have you developed games for Roblox? *Please specify if years or months.*

Q12 Which of the following best describes you:

- Roblox player who has tried to make a game or any component of a game (1)
 - Independent developer (e.g., designer, scripter, developers, etc.) (2)
 - Part of a team of developers (3)
 - Owner of a development team (4)
-

Q13 Over the last six months, around how many hours a week did you spend on game development and maintenance?

- I don't do these most weeks (1)
 - Less than 5 hours (2)
 - 5-10 hours (3)
 - 11-20 hours (4)
 - 21-30 hours (5)
 - 31-40 hours (6)
 - More than 40 hours (7)
-

Q14 Over the last six months, around how much money have you earned from Roblox game development? *Please specify if Robux or USD.*

Q15 Over the last six months, has Roblox game development generally been your:

- Main job: primary way you make money that supports your financial needs (1)
 - Side job: additional or secondary way of making money that complements one's primary source of income (2)
 - Hobby (3)
-

Q16 Over the last six months, which of the following statements best describes the money you have earned from Roblox game development?

- Essential for meeting my basic needs (1)
 - Important for meeting my basic needs, but not essential (2)
 - Nice to have, but not needed for meeting my basic needs (3)
-

Q17 How did you hear about this study?

Q18 What email address can we contact you through?

End of Block: RBLX Game Devs

Start of Block: RBLX Parents/Guardians

Q33 Information for parents/guardians: For those under 18, we need to get a signed consent form from a parent or guardian and will also be scheduling the interview through them. **For the following questions, please only answer for one child per submission. Please ensure that all information is accurate and correct.**

Q34 What is the name of your child that is a Roblox game developer?

Q19 How old is your child that is a Roblox game developer?

Q36 How does your child describe themselves?

- Male (1)
- Female (2)
- Non-binary / third gender (3)
- Prefer not to say (4)
- Prefer to self-describe (5) _____

Q37 Is your child of Spanish, Hispanic, or Latino origin?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
-

Q23 Choose one or more races that you consider your child to be:

- White or Caucasian (1)
- Black or African American (2)
- American Indian/Native American or Alaska Native (3)
- Asian (4)
- Middle Eastern or North African (5)
- Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander (6)
- Other (7)

Q24 How long has your child played Roblox? *Please specify if years or months.*

Q25 How long has your child developed games for Roblox? *Please specify if years or months.*

Q26 Which of the following best describes your child:

- Roblox player who has tried to make a game or any component of a game (1)
 - Independent developer (e.g., designer, scripter, developers, etc.) (2)
 - Part of a team of developers (3)
 - Owner of a development team (4)
-

Q27 Over the last six months, around how many hours a week did your child spend on game development and maintenance?

- I don't do these most weeks (1)
 - Less than 5 hours (2)
 - 5-10 hours (3)
 - 11-20 hours (4)
 - 21-30 hours (5)
 - 31-40 hours (6)
 - More than 40 hours (7)
-

Q28 Over the last six months, around how much money has your child earned from Roblox game development? *Please specify if Robux or USD.*

Q29 Over the last six months, has Roblox game development generally been your child's:

- Main job: primary way you make money that supports your financial needs (1)
 - Side job: additional or secondary way of making money that complements one's primary source of income (2)
 - Hobby (3)
-

Q30 Over the last six months, which of the following statements best describes the money your child has earned from Roblox game development?

- Essential for meeting my basic needs (1)
 - Important for meeting my basic needs, but not essential (2)
 - Nice to have, but not needed for meeting my basic needs (3)
-

Q31 How did you hear about this study?

Q32 What email address can we contact you (parent/guardian) through?

End of Block: RBLX Parents/Guardians
